

Concentrations of some metals in kidneys and liver of goats slaughtered at Atakpa Abattoir, Calabar South, Cross Rivers State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this study was to determine the concentrations of some metals: Cadmium (Cd), Cobalt (Co), Chromium (Cr), Mercury (Hg), Iron (Fe), Copper (Cu), Manganese (Mn), Nickel (Ni), Lead (Pb) and Zinc (Zn) in two organs (Kidneys and Liver) of Goats slaughtered at Atakpa abattoir in order to ascertain if they are within the permissible limits set out by WHO, FAO and ANZFA for meat consumption. The study was carried out within a period of four months, September-December 2014. The samples were taken to Chemistry Department Laboratory where they were digested with 20ml of Nitric acid (HNO₃) and analysed for metals using Perkin-Elmer Analyst Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometry. The Mean concentrations of metals in the kidneys were: Cd, 0.015±0.029mg/kg; Co, 0.00±0.00mg/kg; Cr, 0.040±0.027mg/kg; Cu, 0.050±0.011mg/kg; Fe, 0.084±0.023mg/kg; Hg, 0.00±0.00mg/kg; Mn, 0.054±0.006mg/kg; Ni, 0.038±0.027mg/kg; Pb, 0.00±0.00mg and Zn, 0.099±0.019mg/kg while the mean concentrations of metals in the liver were: Cd, 0.014±0.029mg/kg; Co, 0.00±0.00mg/kg; Cr, 0.046±0.030mg/kg; Cu, 0.062±0.009mg/kg; Fe, 0.107±0.015mg/kg; Hg, 0.00±0.00mg/kg; Mn, 0.061±0.008mg/kg; Ni, 0.044±0.030mg/kg; Pb, 0.00±0.00mg/kg and Zn, 0.110±0.029mg/kg. The concentrations of the metals did not vary statistically ($p > 0.05$) in the organs and therefore were not statistically significant. Total rank score assessment showed that liver had higher levels of metals than the kidneys, although the concentrations of metals in the two organs were within the tolerance limits set out by WHO, FAO and ANZFA. Therefore the buying and selling of these goats at Atakpa abattoir for consumption is recommended but continuous monitoring of these metals is necessary since metals can bio-accumulate in goats over a period of time.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Environmental pollution is one of the problems that pose serious threats to animals and humans worldwide. Pollution resulting from continuous and rapid growth in population, industrialization, transportation and associated indiscriminate exploitation of natural resources has increased in recent years [1]; [2]. Pollution problems associated with incidents of oil spills around automobile repair workshops resulting in metal contamination have been the subject of many reports [3]. Those contaminants are known to contain elevated levels of toxic metals

and metalloids such as Pb, Cd, Hg, Ni, Cr, Fe, Mn, Cu, Al, As, and Zn [4]. These metals are natural components of the environment but high rate of industrialization has been responsible for their wider diffusion and dispersal in the environment [5]. Metals for which there are no nutritional requirements may react with biological system to cause adverse effects. Excessive doses of nutritionally essential metals can also cause adverse effect [6]. Living organisms usually need some of the Heavy metals up to certain level or limits while excess accumulation leads to severe harmful effects [7,8].

Metals tend to bioaccumulate in the environment and biomagnify in food chains where their levels might reach toxic limits even when found in low concentrations in environmental samples [9]. With increasing industrialization more and more metals are entering into the environment and since they are unable to degrade, they enter into the food materials like grasses for goats and from there they ultimately make their passage into the bodies of organisms. Heavy metals when they appear in food chain, they accumulate in plant and animal tissues [10].

Food consumption has been identified as the major pathway of human exposure to pollutants accounting for 90% compared to other ways of exposure such as inhalation and dermal contact [11]; [12]. The risk associated with the exposure to metals present in food products has aroused widespread concern about human health. Therefore monitoring the levels of heavy metals in food chain is of great importance for the wellbeing of all life forms as serious health problems can develop as a result of excessive accumulation of these metals in the human body through dietary intakes [13]. The objective of this study is to determine the concentrations of

metals in the Kidneys and Liver of goats slaughtered at Atakpa abattoir in order to ascertain the suitability of the goat meat for consumption.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Study area

Atakpa is the name of a street located in Calabar South, while Calabar South is one of the Local Government Areas in Cross River State, Nigeria with its Head Quarter's in Anantigha. Calabar South is in Calabar town and covers a latitude of 4°55'N - 4°58'N and longitude of 8°18'E - 8°21'E. It also has a total area of 264km². Calabar features a tropical climate with a lengthy wet season spanning seven months (April-October) and a short dry season covering the remaining five months (November-March). Temperature is relatively constant throughout the year, with average high temperature usually ranging from 25°C-28°C. There is also little variance between day and night temperatures as temperatures at night are generally only a few degrees lower than the high temperature which typically averages falls under 3,000mm of precipitation annually.

Fig. 1. Map of Calabar South showing sampling location

2.2 Sample collection

Fresh samples of kidneys and liver of slaughtered goats were collected from Atakpa Abattoir Calabar South, Calabar. The samples were kept in a labelled plastic bag and stored in cooler boxes containing ice blocks before being transferred to Chemistry laboratory in University of Calabar and kept frozen till analysis.

2.3 Sample preparation and digestion

Twenty grams (20g) of each of the samples was dried up in oven by heating to dryness. The dried sample was ground in porcelain mortar with pestle and stored in the desiccator prior to digestion. One gram (1g) of each sample was digested by adding 20ml of Nitric Acid (HNO₃) to the sample in a digestion tube. The digestion tubes with content was covered and put in microwave oven for extraction. Digestion was carried out at a temperature of 100°C using a kjldahl heating digester until mixture became clear [14]. The sample was cooled and filtered through ashless filter paper into 50ml volumetric flask and made up to the mark with distilled water to determine the various metals [15].

2.4 Elemental analysis of samples

This was carried out in order to determine the concentrations of copper (Cu), zinc (Zn), cobalt (Co), manganese (Mn), mercury (Hg), iron (Fe), chromium (Cr), cadmium (Cd), nickel (Ni), and lead (Pb) in the samples and they were made

directly on each of the final solutions using perkin-Elmer Analyst 300 Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometry (AAS).

2.5 Statistical analysis

Data collected at the end of the analysis were presented in tables and charts and were subjected to T-test statistics at (P<0.05) in order to determine whether the concentrations of the heavy metals varied between the organs (kidneys and liver) of the goats.

3. RESULTS

The concentrations of Cd, Co, Cr, Cu, Fe, Hg, Mn, Ni, Pb and Zn in the kidneys and liver of goats are presented in Table 1 at mean and standard deviation values. All results are expressed in mg/kg. The mean concentrations of metals in the liver were: Cd, 0.014±0.029mg/kg; Co, 0.00±0.00mg/kg; Cr, 0.046±0.030mg/kg; Cu, 0.062±0.009mg/kg; Fe, 0.107±0.015mg/kg; Hg, 0.00±0.00mg/kg; Mn, 0.061±0.008mg/kg; Ni, 0.044±0.030mg/kg; Pb, 0.00±0.00mg/kg and Zn, 0.110±0.029mg/kg while mean concentrations of metals in the kidneys were: Cd,0.015±0.029mg/kg; Co, 0.00±0.00mg/kg; Cr,0.040±0.027mg/kg; Cu,0.050±0.011mg/kg; Fe,0.084±0.023mg/kg; Hg, 0.00±0.00mg/kg; Mn, 0.054±0.006mg/kg; Ni, 0.038±0.027mg/kg; Pb, 0.00±0.00mg/kg and Zn,0.099±0.019mg/kg. The concentration of metals in the kidneys and liver were not statistically different (P>0.05).

Table 1. Mean values, Range and T-test statistics values of metals compositions in the Liver and Kidneys of Goats slaughtered at Atakpa Abattoir in Calabar South, Calabar

Metals (mg/kg)	Organs of Goat		P-Probability	Inference	FAO	WHO	ANZFA
	Kidneys (Mean±S.D)	Liver (Mean±S.D)					
Cd	0.015±0.029 (0.00-0.058)	0.014±0.029 (0.00-0.00)	P>0.05 (NS)	H ₀ accepted	>1	1	-
Co	0.00±0.00 (0.00-0.00)	0.00±0.00 (0.00-0.00)	P>0.05 (NS)	H ₀ accepted	-	-	0.10
Cr	0.040±0.027 (0.00-0.060)	0.046±0.030 (0.00-0.00)	P>0.05 (NS)	H ₀ accepted	-	-	0.10
Cu	0.05±0.011 (0.035-0.058)	0.062±0.009 (0.049-0.070)	P>0.05 (NS)	H ₀ accepted	-	-	200
Fe	0.084±0.023 (0.065-0.117)	0.107±0.015 (0.091-0.127)	P>0.05 (NS)	H ₀ accepted	-	-	0.10
Hg	0.00±0.00 (0.00-0.00)	0.00±0.00 (0.00-0.00)	P>0.05 (NS)	H ₀ accepted	-	-	-
Mn	0.054±0.006 (0.047-0.059)	0.061±0.008 (0.050-0.067)	P>0.05 (NS)	H ₀ accepted	-	-	0.10
Ni	0.038±0.027 (0.00-0.062)	0.044±0.030 (0.00-0.065)	P>0.05 (NS)	H ₀ accepted	-	0.2	-
Pb	0.00±0.00 (0.00-0.00)	0.00±0.00 (0.00-0.00)	P>0.05 (NS)	H ₀ accepted	-	-	>1
Zn	0.099±0.019 (0.071-0.112)	0.110±0.029 (0.071-0.142)	P>0.05 (NS)	H ₀ accepted	0.5	0.5	50

Where; S.D= Standard deviation, NS = Not-Significant, FAO= Food and Agricultural Organisation, WHO = World Health Organisation, ANZFA = Australia New Zealand Food Authority.

The mean variations of metals in kidneys are presented in Figure 2 while mean variations in the liver are presented in Figure 3. The concentrations of Zn were highest in both the

kidneys (0.099 ± 0.019) mg/kg and liver (0.110 ± 0.029) mg/kg respectively. Co, Hg and Pb were not detected in the two organs (kidneys and liver).

Figure 2: Mean variations of metals in kidney of goats slaughtered at Atakpa Abattoir in Calabar South

Figure 3: Mean variations of metals in Liver of goats slaughtered at Atakpa Abattoir in Calabar South

4. DISCUSSION

Zinc had the highest concentrations (0.110 ± 0.029 and 0.099 ± 0.019) respectively in both liver and kidneys. The highest concentration of zinc was found in the liver. [16] found higher levels of copper and zinc in the livers and kidneys of mutton and beef. The high levels of Zn concentrations in liver of the goats are likely due to their special functions; liver as

storage and metabolic organ [17]. Although Zn is an essential metal, its high concentration in organs of goats could pose significant health risks to consumers. Excess consumption of Zn in the diet can result in haematological effects such as anaemia and induction of copper deficiency by hindering its absorption [18]. Zinc is an essential element in human diet. Too little Zn can cause problems; however, too much of Zn is harmful to human health [18]. The

concentrations of zinc in all the samples studied were below the permissible limit 150ppm set by WHO and ANZFA. Copper (Cu) was found to be low in both kidneys and liver. Copper is an essential component of various enzymes and it plays a key role in bone formation, skeletal mineralization and in maintaining the integrity of the connective tissues. Copper is essential for good health, but very high intake can cause liver and kidney damage [18]. In humans, 10-30mg of orally ingested copper from food stored in copper vessels might cause intestinal discomfort, dizziness and headaches while excess accumulation of copper in liver may cause hepatitis or cirrhosis and haemolytic crisis similar to that seen in acute copper poisoning [19]. [20] reported high level of Cu in muscle (4.57mg/kg^{-1}) and liver (31.07 mg/kg^{-1}). [21] reported high level of Cu, 26.6mg/kg^{-1} , 3.04mg/kg^{-1} , 3.94mg/kg^{-1} in muscle, liver and kidney, respectively. However, the copper content detected in the samples did not exceed the permissible limits set out by (ANZFA) Australia New Zealand Food Authority and WHO.

Cadmium concentrations in both samples were found to be low. Cadmium is toxic to virtually every system in the animal body. It is almost absent in the human body at birth; however, it accumulates with age. [22] reported cadmium accumulation in kidneys and liver over a long time that cadmium interacts with a number of minerals mainly Zn, Fe, Cu and Se due to chemical similarities and competition for binding sites. Cd has a long biological half-life of about 30 years in humans [23]. It damages the proximal tubules of nephrons leading first to leakage of low molecular weight proteins and essential ions like calcium into the urine, with progression over time to kidney failure [24]. The mean of detectable concentrations of Cd in the meat parts were lower than 0.161mgkg^{-1} reported by [21] on calves from polluted industrialised areas of Northern Spain and higher than 0.096mgkg^{-1} for those in rural areas. All the mean values were also higher than 0.038mgkg^{-1} reported by [25] on liver of poultry from polluted area in Poland; 0.021mgkg^{-1} reported by [26] in Finland. High Cd levels have been reported by [27] in liver (0.35mgkg) and kidney (0.83mg/kg) of goats from Nigeria, and were ascribed largely to atmospheric deposition and free range grazing. The concentration of cadmium in the samples studied was found to be below the permissible level set by FAO and WHO.

Nickel concentrations were low in liver and kidneys. Ni is known to be a micronutrient. It is present in a number of enzymes in plants and micro-organisms. In humans, it regulates prolactin and stabilization of RNA and DNA structures [28]. However, nickel can cause severe allergic reaction in excessive intake [29]. However, hypothetically, humans require 75mg of elemental Ni per day [30]. [31] reported Ni concentration as 2ppm and 1ppm in mutton and beef, respectively. [32] found Ni concentration in

liver ($0.29:0.19\text{Ng/g}$) and kidneys ($0.16; 0.13\text{Ng/g}$) of cattle and goats. The Ni concentration in the samples did not exceed the permissible limits set out worldwide.

Chromium concentrations in the samples were found to be low. Chromium is an essential element helping the body to use sugar, protein and fat, at the same time it is carcinogenic for organisms [33]. Excessive amounts of chromium (Cr) may cause adverse health effects [18]. [32] reported high concentration of Cr in caprine liver of $1.22\pm 0.21\text{mg/g}$ and low level was reported in meat of beef (0.23 mg/g). The concentration of the metal 0.10mg/kg was below permissible limit set by FAO, WHO and ANZFA.

The concentration of Fe was higher in the liver than in the kidney. [32] reported high concentration of Fe in the liver of chicken ($4.65\pm 0.30\text{mg/g}$) and low concentration in beef (0.98mg/g). Iron (Fe) is an essential trace element and it occurs naturally in plants and animal tissues. Iron is an essential element within the haemoglobin molecule, which carries the oxygen in every red blood cell. It also functions in myoglobin, a molecule that supplies oxygen to muscles.

Daily intake of small amounts of Mn is needed for growth and good health in humans, otherwise deficiency of Mn can cause nervous system problems [34]. Manganese concentration was found to be high 0.061 ± 0.008 in liver and low 0.054 ± 0.006 in kidney but lower than the permissible limits in the two organs. Hg, Co and Pb were below detectable level in the organs. These metals are harmful even when found in minute quantities. But in the course of this research none was found in a detectable level.

5. CONCLUSION

From the results of this study, the concentrations of all the metals in the liver and kidneys of goats slaughtered at Akpata abattoir were found not to be statistically significant ($p>0.05$). Although the concentrations of metals in the two organs were below permissible limits set out by WHO, FAO and ANZFA, preventive measures should be taken in order to prevent human exposure to levels higher than the permissible limits for these metals. There should be control of the use of pesticides, fungicides as well as phosphates and sewage sludge fertilizers to reduce the pollution with these metals. Fodder used in feeding the goats in pen houses should not be harvested from polluted areas such as industrial drainages and oil spilled areas. Concentrations of metals in the organs of goats may be due to industrial and municipal effluent discharges on the environments where fodder are harvested and due to some anthropogenic activities. Thus anthropogenic or industrial activities that can result to accumulation of metals in plants should be minimized since metals bio-accumulate in

organs of goats over time. Continuous monitoring of metals in the liver and kidney of goats sold at Atakpa Abattoir is advised.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

KAO designed the study, performed the statistical analysis, wrote the protocol, and wrote the first draft of the manuscript. AP carried out the field sampling, managed the literature searches and the analyses of the study. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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